

Cover

La compra pública de innovación. Instrumento de colaboración para nuevos escenarios

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<p><i>English Abstract (translation from the original abstract in Spanish)</i></p>	<p>In 2017, the Vic Hospital Consortium's budget exceeded 92 million euros, exceeding, for example, the budget of Cáceres City Council (population 95,917) and similar to that of the University of Girona. In the same year, the budget of the Terrassa Health Consortium was similar to that of the city councils of Tarragona (131,507 inhabitants), Salamanca (144,436 inhabitants) and Castellón (169,498 inhabitants), while that of the Parc Taulí Health Corporation was higher than that of the City Council of l'Hospitalet de Llobregat (257,349 inhabitants) and similar to that of the University of Castilla-La Mancha, which has nearly 30,000 students and 2,300 professors/researchers and was ranked eighteenth in the global ranking of research productivity among Spanish public universities in the period 2015-2016. Is there awareness of this reality when discussing the key agents in the design of new economic models or when designing local development strategies?</p>